

FEATURES OF CATERING BASED ON HALAL STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the prospects for the introduction of Halal catering services on the basis of one of the international standards namely Halal and gives recommendations on its advantage when choosing a restaurant concept in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Ancient archaeological monuments and sacred places of Uzbekistan, unique national cuisine, modern national food system, unique hospitality of our people and the conditions created in our country attract tourists widely.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis dated December 22, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that "... actively attracting world brands to the industry, we must pay special attention to the development of pilgrimage tourism ... gastronomic tourism and other industries."

Today, the country has a long tradition of providing quality services to tourists, which requires modern catering services that fully comply with international standards. Offering high quality of catering service for Muslim tourists, especially from Islamic countries, is one of the important tasks of modern tourism globalization.

The increase in the number of tourists visiting our country from Islamic countries will lead to a new modern demand for catering services.

Taking into consideration the changes taking place in the field of tourism in our country, it also sets new requirements for the public catering system. In particular, today's world tourism is waiting for the introduction to the market of such terms as "halal tourism", "halal food" and related issues.

One of the important tasks is to provide Muslims with halal products based on halal standards while traveling. According to the rules of Islam, every Muslim is obliged to observe the rules of nutrition in accordance with the norms and values set out in the holy books of the religion, and to observe them responsibly.

The term "halal" means "lawful" or "permissible", and in Islam, according to Sharia, "it is allowed to drink and use, not

haram " There is halal food, halal lifestyle, and even halal services. The concept of halal includes not only food and drink, but also products and services that meet any Islamic Sharia requirements in banking and finance, tourism, pharmaceuticals, jobs, technology and transport services.

Islamic halal relationships cover all aspects of life and are based on two sources of Islamic Sharia, the Quran and the Sunnah. Halal food and food consumption means that it is allowed to be consumed in accordance with Islamic laws. Haram, on the other hand, refers to foods that are forbidden by religion.

Compliance with halal principles, especially daily purchases of food, compliance with the food system is the most important condition for Islamic relations.

From an Islamic point of view, foods that are prohibited for human consumption include:

- * Halal animal meat improperly slaughtered;
- * The meat of animals slaughtered under a name other than the name of Allah;
- * Mule, donkey, pork and ivory;
- * Alcohol and toxic substances;
- * All plants are poisonous;
- * Clawed animals such as lions, dogs, minks or tigers;
- * Birds such as owls, eagles, falcons, hawks;
- * Pests such as mice, scorpions, snakes, ants, waterfowl, spiders, bees;
- * Contaminated food products listed above.

In the concept of halal, food prepared for Muslims must be of high quality, safe, hygienic and at the same time halal. It should be noted that the most important aspect is that Muslims will have to earn every piece of food by honest labor. That is, as the food is halal, so the profession by which they earn it should be halal. Any

food bought with money earned by Shari'ah impure means such as robbery, theft, bribery, violence, fraud, etc. is considered haram.

All Muslims believe in the aforementioned teachings propagated by Islamic science. At the same time, they practice these beliefs during their travels. Therefore, based on their needs, it is necessary to analyze the market for "halal" tourism in the country.

The Honest Tourism service is a service created for those who love scarcity and avoid wastefulness, based on family vacations, overnight stays in affordable housing, eating at quality, clean food outlets.

According to world statistics, the number of Muslim tourists is growing rapidly from year to year.

According to research by Mastercard and Crescent Rating, 230 million Muslim tourists are expected to travel domestically and internationally by 2026. Muslim travelers are expected to contribute \$220 billion to the global economy by 2020 and \$300 billion by 2026.

The growth of the Muslim tourism market is influenced by the following key factors:

- ☑ Growth of the Muslim population. In particular, a 75% increase in the number of Muslims between 2010 and 2050;
- ☑ Income growth of the middle class;
- ☑ Increasing travel information;
- ☑ Improving the quality of service for Muslim travelers.

Studies show that many Muslims live in many countries around the world, including India, Australia, Egypt, Bangladesh, China, European countries and Canada. It should be noted that a significant proportion of the world's population today are Muslims. This, in turn, requires significant changes in the modern food

market for the Muslim population, especially the rapid development of the halal food industry.

Asian countries such as Malaysia and Indonesia are contributing to the development of this field through the development of "halal" standards and "halal" research centers.

Mastercard-CrescentRating Global Muslim Travel Index APRIL 2019 has published a rating of the TOP 10 countries serving Muslim tourists and the services provided in them.

1. Malaysia
2. Indonesia
3. Saudi Arabia
4. United Arab Emirates
5. Egypt
6. Turkey
7. Qatar
8. Oman
9. Bahrain
10. Iran

The European food industry is also interested in the production of "halal" products. Some European manufacturers supply halal products to Muslim countries. For example, the Netherlands is engaged in "halal" products, mainly serving the halal markets in Europe, East and Africa. Due to the dangers of food safety in the world, the possibility of spreading various diseases, halal food products for non-Muslims are also preferred by consumers for their added safety, hygiene and quality assurance features. This, in turn, increases the demand for honest goods and services. Based on the foregoing, for the development of tourism today it is important to develop halal food services according to the halal standards created for Muslims in Uzbekistan.

According to statistics, a significant part of foreign tourists visiting our country are citizens of Muslim countries.

The increase in the number of tourists visiting our country, in turn, leads to an increase in the export of tourism services.

Also, taking into account the potential of our country in the field of pilgrimage tourism, the establishment of the Department of Support for Pilgrimage Tourism and the introduction of a visa-free regime for countries such as Malaysia, Turkey and Indonesia have led to an increase in Muslim tourist visits.

Since the demand for halal food services based on international halal standards for Muslims coming to our country is growing, it is important to organize halal food.

In this regard, the restaurant plays a special role in providing tourists with halal food services. When setting up a restaurant, the choice of its "restaurant concept" for an honest dining experience is very important, which requires attention to the following, including:

1. Orientation to the organization of serving halal food in a restaurant.
2. Pay special attention to the rapid accommodation of Muslim tourists.
3. Ensuring the presence of competitors in "halal" nutrition and organizing activities on this basis.
4. "Halal" means new modern and high-quality forms and level of service.

The most important condition of the "restaurant concept" is that today guests want to know in advance what kind of food, atmosphere and new forms and levels of modern and high-quality service in the restaurant.

The concept of the restaurant should reflect everything that can affect the reception of the guest by the restaurant.

Concept development is the process of creating, analyzing and systematizing ideas that create the image of a restaurant. The owner and producer of a restaurant must make a number of difficult decisions, each element of which creates a convenient opportunity for guests to become regular customers.

When choosing a restaurant concept, the focus is on the choice of dishes, family preferences, income level, working environment, quality of life, social conditions, religious beliefs, and so on.

When providing halal food services in restaurants, the following should be taken into account. It:

- Ensuring strict compliance with the requirements of an honest standard for Muslim tourists when providing meals to restaurants;
- formation of a culture of high service in the implementation of the same restaurant service and services provided in all regions of the country;

- organization of control over strict observance of the culture of behavior and clothing of employees serving in the restaurant;

- Ensuring strict compliance with ergonomic requirements, safety and health regulations in restaurants and other catering establishments;

- the formation of labor motivation, taking into account the fact that the overall results of the work of restaurant workers depend on the results of the individual work of each employee;

- Development of a national restaurant categorization system, taking into account the constant use of new innovative programs and technologies, along with the requirements of the standard;

- Creation of a unified electronic database at the republican and regional levels on types, composition, forms and prices for public catering services.

References:

1. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis of December 22, 2017.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", Tashkent, January 5, 2019, No. PF-5611
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2018 No. PP-3609 "On additional measures for the further development of tourism in the Samarkand region in 2018-2019"
4. Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf "Public etiquette", "Hilal-Nashr". Tashkent. 2018 pp. 80-81
5. Global Muslim Travel Index 2019, Mastercard-CrescentRating, APRIL 2019
6. "Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, more than 80,000 words and phrases", "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, Tashkent.
7. Katsigris Kostas, Thomas Chris. Restorer's textbook: design, equipment, design [transl. from eng. Prakofiev S.V.]- M: LLC Publishing House "Restaurant Vedomosti", 2008.-576s: -ISBN 978-5-98176-059-4
6. www.islam.ru/ Islamic information portal March 31, 2019

7. www.stat.uz

8. www.uzbekistonovozi.uz

9. <http://uza.uz>